

Buildings building the city: São Paulo in the Fifties

Abstract

This work is based on the integrated research "Architecture and City: São Paulo 1950s" under development, with financial aid from CNPq, alongside the Department of Architecture and Urbanism at the University of São Paulo (Campus at São Carlos). From the analyses of some paradigmatic buildings, this work intends to establish the relationships between the construction of project and urban concepts.

Thus it is proposed, as a fundamental thesis, that without ignoring the precept features or origin between architecture

and urbanism, every architectural project is a bearer of a concept of the city. The Paulista capital, in the period between the final Vargas stage and the second half of the 1950s represents a particularly rich concept for the discussion of this relation. The period of consolidation as the main Brazilian me Carlos A. Ferreira Martins teaches at the Architecture and Urbanism Department of the EESC-USP-São Carlos. He graduated in Architecture at the FAU-USP. He obtained his MsC degree in History at the Faculty of Philosophy,

Literature and Human Sciences of the USP and PhD at the Polytechnic University of Madrid. metropolis corresponds temporality to the modern language stabilization in the country, in its hegemonic formulation. But even so, this language, with its defined repertoire and origin, had to elaborate new programs and new variety geared towards servicing new demands, public and private, which are specifically metropolitan.

Vertical housing, apart-hotels, shopping strips, multi-use buildings (residential, commercial, and work-related) the new scale placed on buildings

destined for mass cultural consume (cinemas, theaters, concert halls), spaces destined to house new museums and galleries in the so called "internationalized artistic information" represent a set of new problems to the Brazilian architecture. Already one is not about the basic equation between modernity and traditional, between architectonic masterpiece and natural landscape which centralized reflection the 1930s and 40s, but to ponder on the relation between the building and the abstract space of the metropolis as an experimental area of new propositions of urban sociability.

Another dimension of relevant interest not only to understanding the period but also to reflect on the construction condition of the contemporary city is on the relation between modern architecture and "patronage": while the heroic period of the "carioca school" had in the State its institutionalizing agent in the period of accelerated metropolization this role was, at the very least, divided among the private entrepreneurs, given to the nature of the new programs. This change does not mean that the State is no longer a privileged client, but that the demands are now geared toward urban equipment (transportation, health, education) rather than symbolic-representative constructions.

The identification and analyses of these fulfillment allows to aggregate a new dimension to the history of modern architecture more aware of author's monographs than to themes. It also allows at a moment characterized by social conscience, for the need of re evaluating for due worth of urban centers, to recuperate and to debate on the dimension of citizenship present in those structures, that responded to needs of their times, but which pointed out to the perspective of construction of a new urban socializing.

KEYWORDS

Brazilian architecture; Architecture: São Paulo: XXth Century Architecture: Multiple Use Buildings

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